

Elicitation of Data Discovery Contexts: An Interview Study

ARDC user study of data discovery project report

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Executive Summary

Project aim

With the expansion of the open data movement in recent years, the issues of data discovery and data reuse have received more attention from various stakeholders, including (but not limited to); funding agencies, research organisations, researchers, data service providers, data practitioners and end-users. In response to growing global demand, many countries have invested in managing and cataloguing data, promoting data sharing and data citation, and setting up infrastructures for streamlining data access and process. However, fewer resources have been invested to investigate the range of contexts of data discovery faced by researchers, which is a crucial factor influencing data discoverability and leading to data reuse.

As the primary agency to support interdisciplinary data discovery in Australia, the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) leads this project and aims to fill this gap. The project focuses on characterising the contexts of data discovery both within and across disciplines to inform the design and evaluation of data discovery services, through exploring the following questions:

1. How do researchers approach data discovery?
2. How do researchers search for data?
3. What data attributes matter to researchers' data search?
4. What criteria do researchers apply for assessing the relevance and usability of datasets?
5. What are the contexts of data reuse by researchers?

Project methodology

The study design aimed to elicit narratives on the contexts of data discovery through in-depth interviews of leading and emerging researchers as well as research-data specialists. A pre-interview survey captured participant profiles (i.e., research areas, career stage, job roles and sources of data in recent research projects) to inform the interview phase. The research and interview design loosely followed the data lifecycle to gain a holistic understanding of the ways researchers approach searching for, accessing, collecting and processing data as the research process unfolds. However, the interviews also aimed to capture the initiating points of data discovery in 'personal data journeys.' This mixed-method approach within a post-positivist research paradigm provided rich material for more detailed characterisation and thematic analysis based on the survey responses and the interview transcripts.

Summary from interviews

We were privileged to interview 24 participants in partnership with three organisations. The participants hold varied job roles at different stages of their careers. While the majority of participants are engaged with collaborative research projects and have extensive experiences discovering data, we also interviewed PhD candidates and teaching-focused academics who brought different perspectives to the study. We were also able to interview several researchers turned data practitioners who we noted engaged more intensively across the phases of a data lifecycle.

Our findings affirm that data discovery plays a critical role in research development. We find that there are significant technical and social aspects in the research process to enable effective data discovery. Many researchers discover data through navigating known sources, search engines and repositories as a self-developed approach to data discovery with varying outcomes, but also through socialisation - whether through the field of science and/or through the interactions with data custodians. Interactions at both a local (researcher-to-researcher) and/or repository (researcher-to-data manager) level are important to assure researchers of the potential value of data sources for re-use. In addition, researchers also engage with those who can demonstrate analytical tools, facilitate data access through repository and data store protocols as part of the discovery process. Together, both technical and social aspects of discovery form an integral part of how researchers move from data discovery to data selection and reuse.

Specific challenges were described in both the discovery and access phases concerning dedicated repositories. These included; discovering and accessing data from multiple repositories, duplication of datasets from different sources, the magnitude and relevance of search results, smooth data access, and lack of provenance information to make sense of data and have confidence for data reuse, and integrating data with formats and variables that are measured in different ways. Importantly, data discovery is challenging partly due to the nature of research projects (i.e., scope, scale and interdisciplinarity) and the role of research data in different stages of research projects.

The following is the summary of each activity of the data-driven research lifecycle:

Data discovery

- Social networks and word of mouth are the most used sources of discovering/collecting data by researchers. Peer-to-peer engagement as well as direct connections to senior researchers (PhD supervisor, Principal Investigators) are important guides in the process of data discovery.
- Government websites and data portals, as well as journal papers and unpublished reports, are important data sources.
- Being able to access repository staff and data producers greatly supports engagement with collections and navigation of protocols for data access and making sense of data.
- Data search behaviour is characterised by sensemaking processes which can include: searching multiple sources, and the potential to query with known variables / key terms. Sensemaking is also important for understanding data processing approaches linked to specific data sources.
- Early data discovery behaviour is also characterised by diverse approaches which include 'googling it', and searching multiple sources, including known and unknown sources and data repositories. Exploration of data prior to access data typically includes consideration of data attributes. In the empirical sciences these included considerations of; measurement, level of granularity, quantity and coverage of data, familiarity with data capture technologies and suitability of data formats, and quality of metadata (i.e. variables/data dictionary, standards, reliability and re-usability of metadata).
- Data quality was identified as the most critical data attribute by researchers in their data discovery efforts. In most cases, quality was associated with the reliability of the methodology

(established longitudinal studies), the reputation of the institutional repository or the ability to trace the data to its originating principal investigators.

- Established data provenance, notably the historic value of time series and longitudinal data collections, is seen to raise the reputation of data repositories. Related research groups were also valued of importance noted in both the social and ecological sciences.
- Barriers to confidence in discovery directly via data repositories included; duplicated datasets across multiple repositories, as well as the magnitude and relevance of search results.

Data collecting/access

- Data aggregators (government data, data repositories, paid services and data products) are consulted, depending on the research scope and available resources.
- Facilitation of assessing and accessing data by expert staff, even when there were access controls for datasets, greatly enhanced the experience of data collection by researchers.
- Almost all interview participants source data from government agencies. Those with prior experience in government roles were more likely to be aware of specific government data sources. However, researchers also noted greater awareness of open-source data when it was 'promoted' by its parent department.
- Barriers to accessing data included (but were not limited to); dead links to the data, outdated information regarding data custodians or data managers, and data restrictions of confidentiality.

Data processing

- Data processing involves a series of operations to conform to the data structure, organisation and granularity, data integration and data manipulation.
- Documentation of data, including the metadata associated with data and data dictionary, as well as engaging with data custodians and data managers are important considerations. In particular, their role in establishing national, and, in several cases, international standards was key in supporting data translation and exchange across global databases.
- The role of researchers' tacit knowledge and experience about data processing is important.
- Interoperability, data formats and the potential to integrate data were important considerations for several researchers in their identification and use of data.

Data analysis

- Participants commonly used quantitative data analysis techniques and tools, such as statistical software packages (SPSS, Stata, R, MatLab) and other analysis tools (Python, Jupyter Notebook, ArcGIS).
- Tasks performed include data modelling, data extraction, validation of tool and model validation through a list of identified data analysis tools and platforms.
- In collaborative research, some challenges were noted with generational change in modes of analysis through an increase in cloud and API services.

Data reuse

- Data practitioners anticipate the contexts of data reuse by “what we find useful is what other people will want.”
- Data quality is critical for data reuse, as well as provision of data in various formats and platforms, data coverage, and data expertise.
- Data needs given the specificity of research objectives affect data selection criteria and data reuse.
- Clear data licensing and conditions of data reuse are critical.

Data sharing and publishing

- Participants share data through interpersonal interactions (social networks and word of mouth), data aggregators (data repositories and data archives) and research literature in scholarly communication.
- Participants are more likely to publish their data for the public good, satisfying the publishers’ requirements and institutional policy.
- Participants are increasingly recognising the importance of publishing data papers as a way of documentation and promoting datasets and as ‘ready-made’ opportunities for co-authorship.
- Publishing data papers are becoming recognised in scholarly communication and emerging as a measure of research impact for stakeholder interests.

Recommendations

The implications for the design and evaluation of data repositories and suggestions for service provisions of data repositories are presented as follows:

For data collector/custodian

1. Promoting datasets: Organising training workshops for promoting benchmark datasets, and their access and use methods, would be useful for reaching out to researchers and those who want to pursue interdisciplinary and collaborative research projects.
2. Publishing data papers: A published data paper has more information about the steps by which a dataset is collected and processed. Also, researchers trust a dataset more if it has gone through an editorial review process.
3. Provide consistent guides (or standards) about data documentation and data dictionary: Data repositories need to provide detailed documentation of data, high-quality metadata and data dictionary, to enhance interoperability of metadata across repositories and help researchers to discover and integrate datasets from multiple repositories.
4. Enhance provenance and licence information: Data aggregators need to establish a licence of data use, including terms of use and provide provenance information such as data processing details, and contact information of the data custodians and data managers.
5. Establish effective partnerships between data managers and end-users: Data repositories need to re-imagine their roles within the changing scholarly communication system by integrating or

collaborating with the stakeholders in the changing scholarly communication landscape.

For data discovery system operators

6. Enrich and link metadata with sources external to a data repository/catalogue: Data repositories can source the research data from data papers, supplementary materials attached with journal papers, links to data processing codes published on other platforms and build a database for keeping track of data from traditional journal papers and data papers.
7. Enhance user interface design by providing filters for customised data formats: Data repositories can build search interfaces that consider the researchers' needs for both data discovery and data processing, such as the provision of raw data with a specific structure, organisation and granularity.
8. Enhance user interface design by understanding search behaviour: Data repositories need to prioritise the system objectives of meeting user information needs when they are engaged with selecting and using a dataset. For example, enrich index and search interface with data variables: When researchers search for data, they have certain variables in mind. It is important for a data discovery service to index variables, and group datasets from multiple resources around variables.
9. Provide federated search of datasets from multiple repositories with common themes to reduce the user's burden of searching multiple sources and deal with duplicates of data records.
10. Make metadata available together with datasets: This will assist researchers when they analyse a dataset for assessing the fitness of the dataset and use conditions for their research project.

This project has been approved by the Monash University Ethics Committee with application No. 30889.

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Introduction

This project is designed to elicit data discovery contexts from researchers across Australia's research system. As Australia's leading research data coordinating agency, ARDC has identified a need for a greater understanding of the contexts around which data users approach their data discovery journey. Specifically, the study has been designed to answer the following research questions:

- How do researchers approach data discovery?
- How do researchers search for data?
- What data attributes matter to researchers' data search?
- What criteria do researchers apply for assessing relevance and usability of datasets?
- What are the contexts of data reuse by researchers?

Interviews were conducted with the support of ARDC partners: Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Infrastructure (TERN), Australian Data Archive (ADA) and CSIRO, who have their own data discovery services and share an interest in this study. The ARDC partners also supported the project by reaching out and recruiting researchers engaged through their services to participate in the study.

This study adopted a mixed-method approach to answer the proposed research questions by using both survey and in-depth interview methods. A pre-interview survey was designed to capture participant background information, including; their research areas/topics, stage of career, job roles and their data sources in recent projects. We designed the interview protocol along each step of the data lifecycle (after Yong, Zahuranec, & Verhulst, 2021) and adopted a critical incident technique (CIT) protocol to conduct semi-structured in-depth interviews to elicit the contexts of data discovery.

In this qualitative study, the use of the CIT provided a deeper understanding of both *what* motivated participants to perform data searches and *how* participants approach data discovery. In particular, the study aimed to elicit an understanding of researchers' search behaviour, such as; perception of data attributes, relevance judgement and usability of data/datasets, and in what contexts researchers will reuse data. Participants ranged from researcher-data specialists to researchers at different points in their careers, providing rich insights into similar, as well as specific, challenges in data discovery.

ARDC has previously conducted detailed search logs analysis to understand *aggregated data search behaviours* for users' interaction with the Research Data Australia (RDA) data discovery portal. Voluntary online surveys from RDA have also been conducted to provide feedback to the ARDC on *what* people perform data searches. However, the results do not answer the question of how, when and why researchers in particular approach data discovery. This interview study intends to gather insights and a better understanding of the broader context of data search (not limited to RDA) by researchers from different disciplines. The findings will inform ARDC and ARDC partners of how their data discovery service can be enhanced to better serve the target users with diverse interests and disciplinary practices of data reuse.

In this first phase of this Data Discovery Context (DDC) project, we focussed on participants engaged in either the ecological sciences or the social sciences who were also most likely to be engaged via the three ARDC partner organisations: the Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN), the Australian Data Archive (ADA) and CSIRO. These three organisations all have an established data discovery and access portal, and this allowed us to potentially compare and contrast key disciplinary areas.

Methods

This study has been designed to elicit the contexts of data discovery by adopting a mixed-method approach within the post-positivist research paradigm (Williamson, 2018). Specifically, we used the methods of survey and in-depth interviews to understand the broader contexts of data discovery within people's information-seeking processes. A pre-interview survey was administered to learn more about the participant's background, including their research areas/topics, stage of career, job roles and their data sources in recent projects. This information was also used in the follow-up semi-structured in-depth interview. A critical incident technique was used to elicit the contexts of data discovery by asking probing questions (Davenport, 2010; Flanagan 1954). The interview protocol was developed and organised by referencing stages of a data lifecycle.

Interview instruments

After a literature review, we piloted an initial interview protocol with three researchers and subsequently designed a semi-structured interview protocol that more closely followed each step of the data lifecycle (after Yong et al, 2021). These steps were:

- **Collection:** Gathering data from surveys, censuses, voting or health records, business operations, web-based collections, and other relevant, accessible sources. In this report, we will reference data collected by others as secondary data.
- **Processing:** Removing irrelevant or inaccurate information, reformatting contents to be interpretable by analytic software, and otherwise validating the data collection.
- **Sharing:** Accessing the data with relevant collaborators with the intent of deriving insights from it.
- **Analysing:** Assessing the data collection with the goal of extracting insights about the issue they are studying.
- **Using:** Acting on the insights derived. These actions can affect data collected for future operations.

As this study took a particular focus on data discovery context by researchers and those closely engaged in supporting research data curation, we have added the following two more granular stages/activities for fitting a research cycle:

- **Data discovery:** For researchers who seek secondary data, this is the phase of starting their processing of data seeking in the context of their research projects. Based on the research

findings we highlight the intermeshed phases of social as well as socio-technical aspects of data discovery which we note as;

- ‘social discovery’ via communities and word of mouth recommendation in order for researchers to ‘learn about’ a data discovery system.
 - an exploratory period, which often included interacting directly with repository support staff, colleagues and principal investigators, to understand provenance and trusted sources.
 - ‘sensemaking’ as a period of sourcing and testing datasets that were collected by others, which typically included navigating related tools, platforms and access protocols.
- Data and research product publishing: We highlight researchers’ attitudes and challenges in publishing their datasets and other research products, such as coding for models, based on data collected through their research project, which could be (but not limited to) generating new datasets through reusing secondary data.

Pre-interview Survey

In preparing participants for the interview and for interviewers to get to know participants’ research backgrounds, we designed a pre-interview questionnaire as attached in Appendix I. The pre-interview questionnaire has two parts: the first part was to get participants’ consent in participating and recording the interview, and the second part asked: 1) a participant’s background (employer organisation, research topic, job role), 2) information about a recent research project that includes a short description of the project, participant’s role in the project, the funding sources of the project, the stage of the project and any related publication to the project, and 3) activities related to data (e.g. data scoping, data sourcing, data gathering, data transformation, data publishing, etc), types of data and sources to get data.

The pre-interview survey provided a small set of comparative data, but was principally designed as a valuable prompt for starting a conversation with participants. The pre-interview survey also aimed to set up participants’ expectations for the interview and to provide interviewers with some indication of fields of focus, terminologies and acronyms from a research topic.

Recruitment of Participants

ARDC conducted this study in partnership with selected research disciplines that have had a data repository in place so that the findings from the interview will benefit wide communities by improving data discovery practices. The ARDC’s role included; briefing partner organisations on the purpose of the interview study, encouraging partner organisations to provide feedback on the interview protocol and design and promoting and recruiting researchers from their discipline to participate in the study. The ARDC hoped that participants recruited in this way may have experience in searching data from disciplinary data portals, especially the data discovery service offered by partnering organisations. We initially indicated two requirements for participants - a participant should have some experience of 1) discovering other party’s data, i.e. secondary data, for their research and 2) discovering data with any

data repository/catalogue or any other data discovery tool. In this way, the three partner organisations helped to recruit about 22 participants. A further two participants were recommended by other participants.

Data Analysis

We summarise the results from the pre-interview survey and interviews below. The results provide initial findings from an exploratory analysis of the survey and interview transcripts. The survey contributions were captured via Google Forms and exported to Excel. Categorical data, such as stage in research career and phase of research project of focus, were compared in relation to noted levels of engagement with the data life-cycle for a nominated project. These outputs were explored visually to support further analysis of points of interest in the interview transcripts. Interviews were all conducted and recorded via Zoom. We downloaded recordings and transcribed using Microsoft365 transcription tool, followed by hand editing with the sound recordings. We imported the transcripts into nVivo, a qualitative data analysis tool, to annotate transcripts and summarise findings. The interview notes were also used to triangulate the research findings in this study. All software, files and documentation in relation to the project are managed within Google suite and/or hosted under licence by Monash University.

Results Summary

Pre-interview survey

The pre-interview survey captured an overview profile of the participants as well as a snapshot of their field of focus, for example, their job roles, their career stage, as shown in the table below. Participants were asked to nominate a recent project in which they need to discover and/or reuse secondary data and the data sources they could get required data for their nominated project. In summary:

- Majority of participants engaged in collaborative research.
- Majority of projects nominated by participants are funded by the Australian government.
- Majority of participants sourced data from catalogues external to their organisation and website of government agencies.

Domain of Focus	Higher Degree Researchers (HDRs)	Senior Career (SCRs & Data Leads)	Mid Career (MCRs & Data Managers)	Early Career (ECRs & Data Analysts)	
Ecosystem Sciences	2	7	3	3	15
Humanities and Social Sciences	3	1	1	3	8
Physical Sciences		1			1
Totals	5	9	4	6	24

Analysis of interview transcripts: Data Lifecycle

We organise the interview results primarily based on the data lifecycles from the perspectives of data practitioners, together with the perspectives of users for data discovery. Since our interview participants are sourced from data practitioners and end-users of data practitioners (some with dual roles), their responses have provided a more comprehensive picture of how data has been created and managed throughout the data lifecycle. As such, the phase of data discovery has been added to the results. Additional categories of sharing and publishing have been added to reflect other general comments in the study. We also compare and contrast the responses between the data practitioners and the end-users in our analysis, where appropriate.

Summary of findings by Data Lifecycle Stage

Data Discovery

'... Quite often you won't actually just find it through Google search. I guess one challenge is you need to know people. You need to read the literature and know what's out there - quite often cross disciplinary work as well. So sometimes it is really interesting, but it's just not using your discipline, so you wouldn't kind of necessarily identify (it from) the literature that you read.' (P15)

Data Discovery Context

This “data discovery” phase is when researchers start their data seeking process in the context of their research projects by drawing on their disciplinary knowledge. The major activity in this phase is to identify which and where a data source or repository could have datasets they desired for their research project. It is worth noting that a majority of the interview participants in this study are engaged in collaborative research and they may hold multiple roles (e.g., a disciplinary researcher, collaborative researcher and data practitioner), many of them have developed rich information-seeking strategies for data collection.

We identify social interactions as an important source of discovery data, and we further classify data discovery activity into three broad socio-technical interaction categories: interaction with a data discovery system, interaction with information as presented by the discovery system, and data access which inter-relates to data collection.

Summary of findings

- Social interactions were noted as particularly important in the data discovery phase
 - networks and word of mouth were noted as the most important sources for researchers looking to identify new data sources.
 - engagement with repository staff was noted as key to understanding access protocols and effectively navigating data within repository sources.
 - direct contact with Principal Investigators, colleagues and government staff was described as important for ‘trusting’ and understanding how to engage with a data source.
- Socio-technical interactions of data search behaviour typically includes a ‘sensemaking’ stage which is characterised by;
 - understanding tools/platforms associated with data types,
 - searching multiple sources
 - querying with variables,
 - understanding the magnitude and relevance of search results.
- The exploratory phase in data discovery includes decisions about data quality and reliability. Researchers considered important data attributes such as;
 - measurement types
 - information about level of granularity, quantity and coverage; high-quality metadata (i.e. accessible data dictionaries, standards, reliability and re-usability of metadata)
 - familiarity with data and data provenance.

Data Collection and Access

'... Based on my experience, which might not be generalizable, but... it can increase the speed of your having access to the data or whatever you need if you have strong connections with the staff of that ... institute.' (P23)

Data Collection and Access Context

In the data lifecycle, the phase of collecting refers to the initial stage of gathering data from multiple sources by data practitioners. For researchers who seek secondary data, this is the phase researchers access potentially relevant datasets as identified in the “data discovery” phase, and download datasets for further assessment of data usability and fitness for their intended research questions.

Technical barriers noted in this study are similar to those recognised in earlier studies. But those which were prominently highlighted in relation to the repositories in Australia included;

- challenging protocols like requests of using API to access data
- excessive returns to search requests in repository searches
- finding duplicates across different data repositories
- finding dead links to the data, outdated metadata and data restrictions on confidentiality.

Summary of findings

- Data aggregators (government data, data repositories, search engines and paid services and data products) are consulted, depending on the research scope and available resources. Trust in data quality and reliability are key determinants in data collection independent of the research domain - in particular;
 - Almost all participants source some data directly from government departments or agencies.
 - International institutional datasets are highly trusted for quality (e.g. NASA, University associated repositories) as are established global research community initiatives (e.g. FluxNet, World Values Survey).
- Primary data collection is noted to have a substantial influence on researcher considerations of later use, particularly for time series and longitudinal data, e.g. changes to questions in longitudinal social surveys, changes to real-time sensor technologies in ecological studies. Other factors noted include;
 - Practices in accessing and collecting data vary and range from highly managed protocols (e.g. access to population surveys in the social sciences) to open download sources (e.g. direct download of satellite data).
 - Where institutional access is poor, social networks (ie who you know) can be important for researchers seeking to gain access to known data sources.
 - In addition to journal papers and unpublished reports, data papers have gained traction as a source of data collection.
- Barriers to data access included social-technical issues such as poor connection with or identification of custodians and/or data managers

Data Processing

'... so some datasets have an analytical tool ...which allows you to do some data analysis. And that's very helpful. ...but for the majority of the dataset, I think I need to develop my own script to do the analysis. The starting point really is to understand the data structure.' (P6)

Data Processing Context

The phase of processing of a data lifecycle refers to the stage where a series of operations are performed to conform to the data structure, organisation and granularity, data integration and data manipulation. Researchers may discard a dataset (even if it is relevant) if they find it is hard to understand the dataset, unable to align (linkage this dataset) with other datasets, or find the data set of low quality (e.g. a lot of missing values, unexpected outliers, etc.). The role of researchers' tacit knowledge of data processing also forms part of their approach. And a list of data processing tools has been identified.

Summary of findings

- Processing involves a series of operations to conform to the data structure, organisation and granularity, data integration and data manipulation.
 - Participants describe a transition in processing approaches via APIs (e.g. cloudside vs desktop processing) and through different coding approaches between and within research teams (e.g. traditional statistical techniques vs R vs Python).
- Documentation of data, including the metadata associated with data and data dictionary, as well as engaging with data custodians and data managers are important considerations.
- The commonalities and differences in roles of researchers and data specialists in data processing is illustrated in collaborative work, e.g.
 - tacit knowledge about data processing techniques and a focus on file formats, data cleaning and addressing data quality is a shared focus.
 - however, those in more data focussed roles linked to research teams describe approaches to 'shepherd' good data practices in relation to; use of data obtained under licence, storing for sharing, metadata management and other documentation.

Data Analysis

'... (you can query) what happened with the whole population of Australia...? And as it is managed by the Australian Bureau of Statistics they have an initiative called DataLab that you need to get training to go through the semantic procedure, but then you can approach the secure environment and you can do your coding on that data.' (P9)

'... I'm also working on Amazon stuff at the moment to try and get this stuff sent across to Amazon so we can use it with the easy hub and get it in the same place as some of the data from the DataCube stuff. I know ... there'll be a bunch of researchers that are just downloading stuff locally and have things on their hard drive but I just try and sort of reiterate things that, like the path in your code, [it's] really good if they point to network things so that we can find them more.' (P3)

Data Analysis Context

The phase of analysing in a data lifecycle involves the application of quantitative data analysis techniques, such as statistical methods and computer algorithms, such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN) techniques, to perform the tasks of data modelling, data extraction, tool validation and model validation.

This study offered a list of data analysis tools and platforms used by researchers. As part of a consortium of collaborative research, researchers perform data analysis with a common set of research questions. It is worth noting that it is hard to separate analysing from processing in some research studies. Data processing is tool oriented and facilitates analysing while analysing requires more knowledge work.

Summary of Findings

- Analytical models for existing data were often determined by the data source. These included
 - within the system analysis in the case of government social data,
 - via Amazon Web Services or community-based platforms such as [Open Data Cube](#).
 - via direct download where data was extracted / downloaded for further analysis, such as satellite data from NASA to integrate with ground-based data in GIS platforms.
- We identify commonly used quantitative data analysis techniques and tools, such as statistical software packages (SPSS, Stata, R, MatLab) and other analysis tools (Python, Jupyter Notebook, ArcGIS).
- Tasks performed include data modelling, data extraction, validation of tool and model validation through a list of identified data analysis tools and platforms.
- In collaborative research, data analysis is performed with a common set of research questions. However, researchers who cover multiple projects describe challenges of inherited or non-defined research aims and 'pick up and put down' approaches to research analysis and writing up.

Data Use and Reuse

'... what we find useful is what other people will want. ... I guess ... most people do the same sorts of things. So, ... what you need to provide (is) to make something useful. So you need to tell people how things were collected, what time, when, what methods you used, and (how) to analyse things. And then people can work out from that themselves what they can do with each part of that data.' P1

Data Use and Reuse Context

The phase of 'using' in a data lifecycle refers to the stage where users intend to consume the data for research purposes. We identify several dimensions of contexts that enable data reuse, including

- Anticipation of data reuse;
- Expertise in managing data;
- Provision of data;
- Data coverage;
- Data interpretation;
- Data needs, and
- Model validation.

The context of data reuse is particularly important for the design, implementation and evaluation of data repositories because they speak to the objectives of system design.

Summary of Findings

- Data practitioners anticipate the contexts of data reuse by "what we find useful is what other people will want."
- Data quality was seen as critical for data reuse. Proxies for data quality identified include
 - accessibility via recognised platforms
 - organisational data expertise
 - provision of data in various formats and levels of granularity
 - data coverage in terms of both temporal and spatial values.
- Data needs, in view of the specificity of research objectives, affect data selection criteria and data reuse.
 - Both ecological and social studies include examples of dependence on long established collection methods (e.g. longitudinal surveys, Flux tower measurements).
 - However, new collection methods and contexts were also being explored and these demonstrate an evolution in data use contexts.
- Technical expertise in managing data affects data reuse. This includes the provision of data managed as a collaborative resource in various formats, such as
 - the creation of SQL databases (e.g. Oracle) for domain-specific data which could also be considered an aspect of assuring data use and reuse.
 - development and support for NoSQL data discovery supported services.

Data Sharing

'... Everyone in that consortium can immediately access the data just by virtue of being in the group, and other people can apply, and we basically have ... to work with one of the (centre) investigators. And if they say, yeah, I want to work with that person, then you get access. (There are) other things that are in there that are more restrictive.' (P14)

Data Sharing Context

The sharing phase of a data lifecycle refers to accessing the data with relevant collaborators with the intent of facilitating the research process. Researchers can share data within a research group with a copy (e.g. USB), shared drive, storage and data archive. Researchers can also share data outside a research group, such as submitting data with metadata to international repositories and Australian data CloudStor.

Similar to data sources identified in the collecting phase, such as interpersonal interactions (social networks and word of mouth), data aggregators (data repositories and data archives) and research literature, researchers tend to share their research data with these sources. Researchers also create mini-repositories as personal collections. For example, they establish a practice of keeping track of data sources from papers, using the Endnote (reference management software package) library.

Some important issues raised in the study include data ownership, data governance, reducing the concept of embargo for accessing the data, as well as contacting the data custodians or data managers for details about the data processing and analysis, such as methods for the calculation of a specific variable.

Summary of Findings

- Researchers share data via interpersonal interactions (social networks and word of mouth), data aggregators (data repositories and data archives) and research literature in scholarly communication.
- Researchers are more likely to publish their data where they see
 - data as an expected research output for the public good (open data awareness).
 - where a research community is likely to add a data source producer as a co-author in related publications (publication practice).
 - to satisfy the publishers' requirements and/or
 - to meet institutional policy.
 - where data 'products' or 'objects' are seen as a recognised metric in research impact for stakeholder interests.
- Data producers are increasingly recognising the importance of publishing data papers as a way of documentation and promoting datasets. This includes
 - Sharing tools for data processing via platforms such as GitHub (Internet hosting for software development) is well established.
 - publishing data processing and analysis codes in journals as supplement material.
 - Publishing data papers as a form of scholarly communication
- Clear data licensing as conditions of data reuse is seen as critical for researchers to view the data publication output as trustworthy - i.e. that attribution will be granted to the originator/s of the data.
- Sharing can also be at the level of an institutional arrangement - for example in the case of sensor data from Australia being shared with NASA.

Data Publishing

'... The concepts of Fair Data weren't in my mind at the time, but it just seemed to make sense to me to do it this way ... It only turns out to be a really good idea several years down the track, so this was somewhat serendipitous, but the format that I chose (was) a particular file format called netCDF which allows you to package metadata and data into the same file.' (P13)

Data Publishing Context

We add the publishing phase to the original data lifecycle to capture the distribution of data to the public.

Within the open science and open data movement and driving forces of collaborative research, researchers are more likely to publish their data for the public good, satisfying the publishers' requirements and institutional policy (e.g. CSIRO mandate). Some researchers who are data collectors also publish their data to institutional repositories or as data papers. However, some researchers will not publish data unless it is required by publishers.

High-profile data publication has demonstrated the usefulness of data for the research and broader communities. Data publication has gained more recognition in some research communities.

Other important considerations for data publishing include the issue of data licensing, restrictions for data reuse and data provenance.

Summary of Findings

- In terms of platforms and repositories, participants noted:
 - An emerging role for repositories as data publishers in their own right - noting the processes required to achieve this status. In some cases, publication platforms act as storage services - particularly in the case of large datasets
 - Google Dataset Search is used as a platform to publish large datasets.
- Researchers noted seeing an increased return to value for publishing data via citations earned:
 - Since data papers are assigned a DOI (digital object identifier) and can be accessed and cited within the peer-review system, research impact for stakeholder interests is being increasingly recognised.
 - In particular, this has incentivised publishing in the case of research community platforms where contributions are made to global datasets.
 - Data processing scripts are routinely published and shared via GitHub.
- Publication formats were of interest both for metadata quality and future discovery. In particular researchers noted value in
 - Being able to create a single file (i.e. netCDF - eg CSV format plus metadata)

Research Findings and Recommendations

In this study we have recruited a diverse group of interview participants in partnership with three organisations. The participants hold varied job roles at different stages of their careers. They are all engaged with collaborative research projects and have extensive experience discovering data for research purposes. Data practitioners engage with all the phases of a data lifecycle. There are disciplinary differences in approaches to data discovery. However, data attributes associated with data quality have been identified as the matter regarded highly by researchers for data discovery regardless of discipline. Data discovery is noted to include periods of social engagement with data creators and custodians as well as socio-technical engagement through exploratory tools. Data search behaviour is characterised by searching multiple sources, including known and unknown sources and data repositories, as well as querying with variables.

Specific challenges include the duplicates of data from different sources, the magnitude and relevance judgement of search results, smooth data access, and lack of provenance information or ‘original’ custodian / creator to make sense of data. Overall, the research results organised by the phases of a data lifecycle have provided a detailed understanding of user data discovery from the perspectives of research data management. In this section, we summarise the overall findings and provide some implications or recommendations for enhancing user experiences of data discovery.

How do researchers approach data discovery?

‘... mostly (for finding) other sources, I would say the first one would be word of mouth. So people know or find out from others what data is available. (If someone else said) ‘... it was really good.’ OK, I’ll go ahead and use that for my research. So word of mouth is really important. (P13)

Researchers’ data discovery journey is embedded in their information-seeking environments. This is reflected in the use of multiple data sources for seeking data. The data sources include interpersonal interactions (social networks and training workshops and seminars), data aggregators (government data, data repositories, search engines and paid services and data products) and research literature in formal journal publications or grey literature. Word of mouth has been frequently mentioned by the interview participants as the main data source. Since experienced and senior researchers can build up their social networks over time, it is more likely that they can rely on their networks to access data. For early-career researchers, their data sources mainly come from their affiliation with a research laboratory, supervisors’ networks, attending training workshops and seminars and participation in a consortium of collaborative research projects. The nature of research projects (i.e., collaborative, interdisciplinary, or single project) also affects how researchers approach data discovery.

Regarding data aggregation, our findings suggest that the data from government or international agencies are important sources for both data practitioners and end-users. However, there are some barriers to data access, such as the granularity in spatial and temporal coverage, diversity in social science, raw data vs. processed data and conditions of use (e.g., unclear licensing information). Approaching data discovery by data aggregators is linked to data processing since researchers and data

practitioners need provenance information about the methods of data collection and the processes of generating data products to support their tasks. Other important considerations include the documentation of data, metadata and data dictionary associated with data, as well as engaging with data custodians and data managers. That is, getting access to researchers' tacit knowledge about data processing, provenance and licensing information are very important considerations in reusing data.

Since the research literature in formal journal publications or grey literature are still important data sources, researchers have found the data in journal papers by using general search engines, Google product suite (e.g., Google Data Search, Google Scholar and Google Earth), data repositories and domain-specific databases, or by word of mouth (e.g., sharing of data through social networks). Publishing data as data papers (i.e. peer-reviewed descriptions of the dataset) in high-profile venues has demonstrated the usefulness of data for the research community, as well as the recognition of data curation efforts by researchers and data practitioners. Since data papers are assigned DOI (digital object identifier) and can be accessed and cited within the peer-review system, it has been considered a measure of research impact for stakeholder interests, including (but not limited to) governments, research funding agencies, universities and research institutions, researchers and data practitioners.

Based on these research findings, we recommend that:

- ARDC and partners support engagement workshops for PhD students and early career researchers to raise the awareness of data services among researchers, to enable interaction with lead data custodians/creators and to gain opportunities to explore data with tools of interest.
- ARDC and partners support training workshops for those seeking to pursue interdisciplinary and collaborative research projects to facilitate a data reuse ecosystem by recognising access protocols and use of relevant data in a discipline, including data citation values and data paper publication opportunities.
- ARDC and partners build data creator profiles for repositories and provide researchers the option to develop their 'data creator profile' to showcase their contribution to data curation and reuse.
- ARDC and partners establish and encourage an appropriate licence of data reuse, including terms of use, through the provision of detailed user guides for data processing details, provenance information of data and contact information with data custodians and data managers.
- ARDC and partners build a database for keeping track of data from traditional journal papers and data papers by sourcing research data from data papers, supplementary materials attached with journal papers, links to data processing codes published on other platforms.

How do researchers search for data?

“... And so I had to do some research to find out what is considered to be the best ozone data ... I got that by doing a rapid literature review... Turns out, the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute is in charge of the best satellite ozone data.” (P14)

Researchers’ search behaviour of data discovery is characterised by searching multiple sources, querying with variables, duplicates among data repositories, as well as magnitude and relevance of search results from user perspectives. In line with the findings of Krämer et al. (2021), our findings suggest literature research is integral to dataset search. That is, the phases of data discovery and data processing are intertwined research processes. For example, our findings reveal that important considerations of performing data processing include the documentation of data, metadata and data dictionary, as well as engaging with data custodians and data managers. As such, researchers contact data custodians or data managers due to not having enough information (data capture method, variables, data gap filling models, etc.) in metadata or getting help to have better understanding of the data.

In this study most researchers need data from multiple sources, such as interpersonal interactions, data aggregators, research literature and search engines. They are frustrated by the difficulty of finding relevant data efficiently from each source. For example, some participants know exactly which government agency has the data they would like to have; for others, they ‘Google it.’ While researchers describe usually starting a search session with known/desired variables, sometimes a search may also lead to serendipitous finding.

However, in numerous cases, participants described the challenge of dealing with duplicates (or equivalents) due to metadata syndication across repositories. Different repositories can also be challenging for researchers because of the complexities of search interfaces and not knowing how the search system works (e.g., not understanding why some metadata records are retrieved and included in a search result list, how to deal with too many search results and how to refine search results). Importantly, a Google-style search interface will not suit the needs of researchers for data access since data search is featured by querying with variables and berry-picking (i.e., finding data from multiple sources, not a one-shot deal). As the researchers’ understanding about the topics evolve as the search activities progress, tacit knowledge about data processing becomes important for data discovery. In a number of cases, participants note searching for a known researcher in a repository, rather than the dataset topic once they are familiar with the research community ‘data’ leaders.

Based on these research findings, we recommend that:

- Data repositories need to provide detailed documentation of data collection and processing processes, high-quality metadata and data dictionary, as well as approachable contact information for engaging researchers with data custodians and data managers.

- Data repositories can expand the sources of data as suggested by researchers, and build search interfaces that consider the researchers' needs for both data discovery and data processing, such as the provision of raw data with a specific structure, organisation and granularity.
- Provide federated search of datasets from multiple repositories with common themes to reduce the user's burden of searching multiple sources and deal with duplicates of records. Some examples include the OCLC WorldCat (a union library catalogue) and EZproxy (electronic resources access and authentication service).

What data attributes matter to researchers' data search?

'... so with administrative data, it's capturing policy and service delivery activities and so sometimes there might be changes to the policy rules that are not documented in the administrative datasets, so the data item - the variable can remain the same, but the meaning of the data item could change. And then there are other datasets that have really poor documentation. And so, ... that's actually something that is actually not well coordinated, right?' (P12)

In this study, we identify the data attributes by the broad categories of 1) Data itself; 2) Research issues; 3) Metadata and documentation; 4) Contacts. Specifically, data attributes can be characterised in terms of measurement, level of granularity, quantity and coverage. For example, whether the data is in the form of raw data or synthetic (i.e. direct measurement vs. non-direct measurement) is an important criterion for assessing the usability of a dataset. Accessing the raw data is preferable because it can be further integrated into other sources or manipulated for other purposes in data reuse. Researchers also consider these attributes in the discovering and processing phases of information-seeking activities.

Since data discovery is linked to specific research objectives, the important research considerations include whether the data is fit for purpose or reused by others who are not familiar with the data. Since researchers use their domain expertise to assess the relevance of data, familiarity with data (i.e. inferring the quality from similar sources), data provenance and data usage history (i.e. data has been reused by others) are important data attributes for researchers to assess the reusability of data.

Regarding metadata and documentation of data, high-quality metadata consists of the following attributes: data dictionary, reliability and re-usability of metadata, data access conditions and data licence, documentation about the data collecting process and whether the standard classification systems are followed. Participants commented on the value of the data dictionary in their decision to utilise a dataset based on the potential to select data for analysis from a dataset. Since a data dictionary serves the function of filtering out the variables that researchers are not interested in or helping researchers find the specific variables of interest in data discovery, it can be used to design search systems to support user search behaviour of querying with variables in data repositories¹.

The reliability and re-usability of metadata are concerned with the feasibility of data and associated metadata for data reuse. Additionally, researchers look for high-quality data with detailed

¹ <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/pages/ICPSR/ssvd/> is a good example of search/compare variables in social science research.

documentation about the data collection processes and following standard classification systems. For instance, if variables like occupation are named consistently so that they can be compared across studies in social science research. However, participants from across the disciplines noted the challenge in selecting data via field titles between datasets.

Finally, whether the data custodians or data collectors can be contacted is important for learning more about the data for data reuse, which may not be detailed in the metadata and documentation of data. This information is useful for further data processing and analysis, such as process methods of a data product for calculating a specific variable.

Based on these research findings, we recommend that:

- Data repositories need to source high-quality primary data for data reuse by enabling querying with variables, providing user guides with metadata in compliance with community standards and updated contact information of data providers.

What criteria do researchers apply for assessing the relevance and usability of datasets?

'... You've sort of done a look at the data dictionary. Got an idea of what is available. Yeah, so you can fairly much go straight in and then find that or what's the experience of finding what you need based on that preliminary review.'
(P15)

As discussed in the previous section about the data attributes that matter to researchers, researchers consider these data attributes in data search. Depending on the search contexts, researchers have applied these data attributes as selection criteria for assessing the relevance and usability of datasets. we identify the following selection criteria:

- Data dictionary
- Data documentation (including data paper, provenance information, uncertainty/limitation of data, processes and models involved in collecting, generating, or correcting a dataset)
- License of use, including terms of use
- Version (and information about each version)
- Required granularity, coverage and completeness of a dataset in terms of spatial, temporal, or any measurement of a data variable
- Information about data access URL/API
- (Approachable) point of contact for data request
- Data format according to community standards
- Consistency between metadata and data on described attributes
- Evidence of data being reused

Our research findings suggest that the line between using and selecting a dataset is not clear, given the complexities of research contexts, including the research environment, career stage, job roles and

nature of research projects (e.g., scoping, multidisciplinary/interdisciplinary and collaborative). Using and selecting a database in data discovery is an iterative search process by consulting multiple resources, interactions with different search systems - such as search engines, proprietary databases and data repositories. The identified selection criteria can be further investigated to determine the relative importance of these selection criteria in different stages of a research project and phases of a data lifecycle.

Based on these research findings, we recommend that:

- Data repositories need to prioritise the system objectives of meeting user information needs at the level of using and selecting a dataset. Using a dataset involves complex processes of performing secondary data analysis in a research project.

What are the contexts of data reuse by researchers?

'... There's never, rarely a case of like, OK, we can just use that dataset. It's kind of a whole bunch of datasets and then trying to sort of look at the metadata. If the metadata isn't useful enough, you often need to ... actually visualise it in GIS, ... or if you're wanting to really see it in context with other data, then you'd need to download that data, put it somewhere.

If you've got someone like me in your ear, then ... I need to also download some metadata or create the metadata and all this stuff and then I can have a look at it.' (P3)

In this study we identify several dimensions of contexts that enable the data reuse, including 1) Anticipation of data reuse; 2) Expertise in managing data; 3) Provision of data; 4) Data coverage; 5) Data interpretation; 6) Data needs, and 7) Model validation. The contexts of data reuse are particularly important for the design, implementation and evaluation of data repositories because they can support the identification of specific objectives of system design. For instance, the data quality is exemplified by the perceived expertise of data providers, the provision of data in suitable formats for data processing and data analysis and the coverage of data needs to be complete in space and time. The categories of data interpretation, data needs and model validation are concerned about the researchers' interaction with data, relevant to the aforementioned data quality metrics of 1) scientifically accurate (e.g. validated against a reference, plausible); 2) details on strengths, limitations, known issues, including availability of uncertainty information, and 3) technically correct/having passed sanity checks (e.g., no unexpected gaps in the time series, consistency between data and metadata).

As revealed in the study, data reuse is a social process. Researchers use multiple data sources for collecting and discovering data through their social networks, data aggregators and research literature, or they are part of a consortium of collaborative research projects. The anticipation of data reuse is relevant to the archiving policy of data repositories and how the data can be curated to meet the needs of researchers. From the perspectives of data practitioners, "what we find useful is what other people will want" highlights the importance of data provenance information for data reuse since the research publication is built on a peer-reviewed system. The publication of data papers in high-profile journals

has made the data more visible to the research ecosystem. From the perspectives of researchers, the research literature regarding cross-referencing for taxonomy can be useful for reusing a dataset, and a dataset reused and cited by other researchers in peer-reviewed publications would carry more weight in selecting and using a dataset for data reuse. Some social science researchers wish to be involved in the data collecting process for including variables they desire to collect for their research. Overall, our findings suggest that data repositories have facilitated the use of existing datasets for secondary data analysis in some disciplines. Data reuse is a social process since we have witnessed the emergence of data papers and the acknowledgement of citing datasets in scholarly communication.

Based on these research findings, we recommend that:

- Data repositories need to re-imagine their roles within the changing scholarly communication system by integrating or collaborating with the stakeholders in the changing scholarly communication landscape.

Conclusion

The project has characterised the contexts of data discovery both within and across disciplines by an interview study with ARDC partners which all have an established data discovery and access portal. Our findings suggest that there are significant technical and social aspects in the research process to enable effective data discovery. Researchers' data discovery journeys are embedded in their information-seeking environments, such as their known data repositories, social networks and part of a consortium of collaborative research projects. However, researchers face challenges in discovering data from a single data repository - in particular when the required data for a research project have to be discovered and synthesised from multiple data repositories. Both metadata and data quality have been identified as critical for data discovery and data reuse regardless of discipline. For those with significant experience in data discovery, there was greater recognition of the need for data governance and the importance of data publication for re-use.

Based on our initial findings we aim to provide further analysis of the rich material offered. The study will also be extended to consider data discovery in other domains to help inform future data repository design, services and engagement.

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